

DRAPING OF WOVEN COMPOSITES OVER IRREGULAR SURFACES

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SUMMARY: The aim of the present work is to provide the basis for developing a drape model intermediate to the two approaches used in the past: namely kinematic modelling and a comprehensive finite element analysis of the drape process. The former approach, while being simple, lacks the completeness and the accuracy due to omission of draping forces and detailed fabric properties. The latter finite element approach of modelling fabric drape requires long processing times and a large amount of input data. The 'next-generation' drape model expected to evolve from the work presented in this paper aims to provide for the secondary effects of draping forces on the fabric deformation. Firstly, measurements of a draped fabric over a relatively complex industrial component are compared with predictions from a kinematic model. Details of the tow deformations are analysed, and it is observed that the deformation varies according to the symmetry of shear. Consequently, uniaxial tests on fabric specimens with asymmetric loading are performed. The paper discusses how these results could be used to develop the next-generation drape model. The same model with suitable properties for the cured composites can be used to carry out the structural analysis of the composites. A prototype model has been implemented and results are presented here.

KEYWORDS: Draping, Woven Composites, Fabric Shear, Kinematic Model.

INTRODUCTION

Woven composite materials have become of increasing interest in many areas of engineering due to the ability of a woven fabric to conform to complex double curvature shapes. It has been observed that, irrespective of the underlying weave geometry, the fabric undergoes nearly pure shear during draping, with the constituent tows rotating freely at the crossover points [1]. The drape behaviour is therefore often simply modelled by mapping these crossover points over the curved mould shape; examples of the work in the past are [2-4], a variation of which has been implemented into the commercial MSC Patran software Laminate Modeler [5]. This output is then used to determine the relative orientation of the yarns over the mould surface and its effect on the mechanical properties of the final composite. Advantages of this approach (termed 'kinematic' modelling) are simplicity and speed of calculation. However, it is likely to be increasingly inaccurate for components which do not have uniformly curved surfaces. They also ignore fabric properties, thereby resulting in the same draped pattern irrespective of

whether the fabric is a prepreg, thermoplastic, or dry perform. Moreover, it may be difficult to make accurate predictions of the composite's mechanical properties, since these models do not take into account the forming loads and tow-level deformation of the fabric, such as inter-tow slippage, change in tow waviness and lateral compaction due to tool contact pressure. At the other end of the spectrum are comprehensive deformation models based on metal forming. An example is the commercial software ESI PAM/FORM [6]. This software, which uses finite element analysis, has been successfully used to simulate the interaction of the woven ply with the tool as it is deformed [7,8]. Several input parameters, such as the blank holder pressure, fabric shear stiffness, tool velocity, ply/tool and ply/ply friction parameters are needed. Although the method overcomes most of the problems associated with the kinematic model, it requires significant computer power.

The aim of the present work is to provide the basis for developing a drape model intermediate to the above two approaches. The work is part of a larger project which aims to provide the fundamental understanding and materials characterisation for the draping of fabric based composites (prepregs, thermoplastic and dry fabrics). The paper first presents the results of the measurements of draped fabric over a relatively complex industrial component, which are compared with predictions from a kinematic model. Details of the tow deformations are experimentally analysed, and it is observed that the deformation varies according to the symmetry of shear and the degree of curvature. Consequently, uniaxial tests on fabric specimens with asymmetric loading are performed to analyse the effects of the membrane forces on the fabric drape. A prototype of an improved drape model is presented.

DRAPE ANALYSIS OF A HELMET

To investigate draping behaviour over a complex shape, the rear half of a helmet was draped using the diaphragm forming of a CFRP twill weave fabric (by DERA Farnborough). Laminate Modeler was used to simulate the kinematic draping over this surface, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Draped pattern over a helmet: kinematic model (Laminate Modeler)

Shear angle measurements over the base of the component were made using a video microscope. These are compared to predictions from the kinematic model Laminate Modeler in Fig. 2. Although predictions are in general good, they lose accuracy near the areas of sudden change of curvature. Note specifically regions A, B and C, which are discussed later.

Fig. 2 Comparison of measured and predicted shear

The yarn slippage was found to be low, and did not seem to follow a particular pattern. However differences in tow deformation were seen in different draped regions, and so it was felt necessary to look at slippage as part of the overall tow deformation.

TOW DEFORMATIONS AND EFFECT OF ‘ASYMMETRIC SHEAR’

Measurements over Helmet sample

Fig. 3 shows two regions near the base of the helmet, with similar magnitudes of shear, but different orientations of the tows with respect to the drape direction, which is vertically downwards in the figures. Fig. 3 shows that the geometry of the tow deformation is markedly different in the two cases.

(a) Symmetrically sheared region A

(b) Asymmetrically sheared region B

Fig. 3 Details of the tow deformation in the draped helmet

These observations were confirmed by local measurements of tow width and spacing at different areas of the helmet specimen. It was found that in regions of symmetric shear (e.g. A), there is little slippage between the yarns, but there is a significant reduction in the tow width

near the crossovers. In asymmetric shear regions (e.g. B) the tow width is more uniform but the tows normal to the drape direction slip significantly.

Asymmetric shear tests

The above observations suggest that the behaviour of a woven fabric under asymmetric shear will be important in developing an accurate drape model. In-plane forces developed in the fabric will change the way the fabric deforms as it is draped, and hence the draped configuration. Coupon tests therefore need to be performed to measure this effect for specimens loaded at various angles to the fibre directions. The stiffness and strength of the fabric and the extent of tow deformation are expected to depend significantly on the loading direction.

The following rectangular specimens were prepared, as shown in Fig. 4 (θ_1/θ_2 implies a sample with the two sets of yarns inclined at θ_1 and θ_2 degrees to the axis of the specimen, with $\theta_2 = \theta_1 - 90$): +90/-0, +80/-10, +70/-20, +60/-30 and +45/-45.

Fig. 4 Specimen dimensions for asymmetric shear tests by uniaxial tensile loading

The prepregs used in the analysis had the following specifications: Hexcel 8552 matrix, Hexcel AS4, 6K fibres, 5-harness satin weave, 0.5mm thick, 597 gsm weight density. The specimens were loaded in an Instron tensile testing machine, at the rate of 10mm/min.

Images of three of these specimens after the tests are shown in Fig. 5. All specimens except the +90/-0 specimen showed nonlinear stress-strain behaviour. The +90/-0 sample failed by rupture of the yarns. For other specimens, the load-strain curve rises sharply as the fibres rotate to align themselves along the load direction. Extreme slippage of the yarns was observed in the +70/-20 and +60/-30 specimens. The +60 yarns in the +60/-30 specimen rotate by almost 35 degrees (compared to 15 deg. for the -30 yarns); this explains why the deformation and the slippage associated with them is higher than in case of symmetric shear. The deformation of the +45/-45 specimen was more regular and included mainly rotations of the tows with little slippage.

Fig. 5 Three test specimens at the end of the tests

Axial load during the test was recorded and plotted as shown in Fig. 6. The elastic modulus of

the fabric along yarn directions given by the slope of the stress-strain curve for +90/-0 specimen was approximately 8 GPa. The tensile strength was 370 MPa.

Fig. 6 Tensile stress-strain curves for the asymmetrically loaded specimens

A simple model based on classical laminate theory (CLT)

Classical laminate theory [9] allows the calculation of properties of a laminate by combining the properties of its constituent UD layers, and suitably transforming them to the load direction. This method has traditionally been used for studying the deformation behaviour of cured laminate composites. Using the same approach one can analyse a woven fabric too, by splitting it up into two θ_1 and θ_2 degrees UD layers, noting however that the behaviour of a soft fabric prepreg is different from that of a cured composite. The deformation involved is large, and highly non-linear. Also, the material is visco-elastic, and time and temperature dependent. The first problem can be overcome by introducing a nonlinear extension to the CLT approach, in which the fibre angles are continuously updated for each infinitesimal strain induced in the specimen, thereby updating the laminate property itself as the deformation continues. Secondly, the time and temperature factors are eliminated by assuming that all the fabric specimens are loaded at the same rate and at same temperature. The model would thus allow explanation of the shape of the graphs and not necessarily the exact magnitude of stresses and strains. Another important assumption made in this model is that the yarns are allowed to rotate freely, i.e. frictional resistance to rotation at crossover point is negligible. Tow compaction and other through-thickness deformations are also ignored.

Consider a fibre which is inclined at an angle θ_0 of to the loading direction, as shown below. Let E_l be the modulus of the fabric in the yarn direction. Let the yarn rotate by an angle $d\theta$ while the fabric extends by an amount dx .

Fig. 7 A single fibre under a uniaxial force

The stiffness of the fabric prior to the infinitesimal deformation is a function of the fibre angle and is given by [9] (with usual notations):

$$\frac{1}{E_x(\mathbf{q})} = \frac{c^4 \mathbf{q}}{E_1} + \frac{s^4 \mathbf{q}}{E_2} + c^2 \mathbf{q} s^2 \mathbf{q} \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\mathbf{u}_{12}}{E1} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $c=\cos$, and $s=\sin$. E_1, E_2 and G_{12} refer to the moduli of the UD ply in the yarn directions. Note that the values of E_2 and G_{12} will be negligible compared to E_1 . When the yarn undergoes a rotation from θ_0 to θ_t (at time t) the following geometric relations hold [10]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_x &= \ln \frac{\cos \mathbf{q}_t}{\cos \mathbf{q}_0} \\ \Rightarrow \cos \mathbf{q}_t &= e^{\mathbf{e}_x} \cos \mathbf{q}_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Thus, knowing the initial orientations of the fibre and the strain \mathbf{e}_x , one can determine the new orientation of the fibre. The longitudinal stress the material undergoes in doing so is given by:

$$\mathbf{s}_x = E_x \mathbf{e}_x \quad (3)$$

A woven fabric has two sets of yarns. The initial orientation of the other set of yarn is given by $\theta_{20}=90-\theta_{10}$. The total force is a sum of the forces needed to deform both the sets of yarns.

$$\begin{aligned} F_x(t) &= [\mathbf{s}_x(\mathbf{q}_{1t})A_{1t} + \mathbf{s}_x(\mathbf{q}_{2t})A_{2t}] \\ A_t &= A_0(\cos \mathbf{q}_0 / \cos \mathbf{q}_t) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where notations 1 and 2 are used to denote the two sets of the fibres. Equations 1 to 4 can be used to determine the load-strain relationship of a woven fabric when it is initially orientated at an angle to the loading direction. The two angles are continuously updated during the nonlinear analysis. A limit on the final value of θ_t is imposed which is equivalent to the locking limit of the fabric (assumed 70°). The expected load-strain curves were plotted for all the experimental samples discussed before. These are shown below and can be compared to the plot in Fig. 6.

Fig. 8 Load-strain plots: theoretical

From the plot, one can determine the pre- and post-locking stiffness of the fabric in the direction of the applied load. This information, coupled with the prediction of slippage and tow

compaction due to an asymmetric load would result in a more accurate drape model. The CLT based model ignores the matrix effects but it does provide a simple way of explaining the asymmetric shear of woven fabrics, and helps us to envisage the utilisation of a similar model in order to develop a more comprehensive drape model, which will include the matrix viscosity.

OUTLINE OF AN IMPROVED DRAPE MODEL

Experimental investigations into the bias and picture frame tests on fabric preregs have indicated that the deformation of the fabric is dependent upon the direction and magnitude of the membrane forces developed. Further verification of the same using a prototype model was needed to justify the usefulness of a comprehensive drape modelling approach. One such approach is to model draping as a mapping as well as a forming problem, taking the moulding forces into account and incorporating their effects on the tow deformation. It is expected that the accuracy of draping will be enhanced due to the inclusion of membrane forces.

Fig. 9(a) shows the outline of the proposed drape model. The sequence of steps involved in the model are listed below:

1. Drape an annulus of the fabric using a kinematic model.
2. Apply membrane forces, model FE mesh and run the analysis.
3. Update the draped pattern and repeat steps 1 and 2 on the updated draped pattern until whole of the fabric area has been draped.
4. Use the final updated draped pattern and FE mesh to carry out the structural analysis.

Fig. 9 Overview of the progressive drape model

The loading on the draped pattern reflects the draping scenario. The draped pattern is loaded along the draping direction, which is the direction of the tool travel. The yarn segments in the draped pattern are modelled as beam or truss elements. The truss elements are allowed free rotations at the crossover points, while the beam elements are effectively welded at the crossovers. Interaction of the fabric with the tool is modelled as a contact analysis problem, with the tool acting as a rigid surface.

Since this analysis was to be used as only a prototype, the focus was on making use of the available software tools. The following are the assumptions made in the analysis.

1. The matrix contribution in the fabric deformation is assumed to be negligible, and so the matrix properties are not considered.
2. Tool-ply friction is ignored for this analysis.
3. The contact between the fabric and the mould is assumed to be hard (i.e. the fabric does not penetrate through the mould surface).

The first two assumptions are part of the simplification intended for the prototype model implementation. These will be removed from an improved progressive drape model to be developed later.

Two surfaces were analysed: a hemisphere of 100mm radius, and the helmet back-skin (approximate overall dimension: 230x220x125mm) supplied by DERA. Fig. 10 shows the displacement plot for a cut view of the helmet surface. The white lines indicate the draped pattern arising out of the kinematic model, while the superimposed darker lines show the deformed pattern after the membrane force analysis. The scale shows displacement magnitude. Red arrows show the nodal force vectors. The nodes at the top of the helmet are clamped, indicated by a grid of thick light blue dots. Beam elements were used for the helmet example.

Fig. 10 Displacement magnitude plot for helmet, max. displacement 0.73 mm.

The maximum nodal displacement at the base of the helmet is approximately 0.4 mm. The fibres in the symmetric shear areas have undergone rotation at the crossovers while those which lie more or less along the load direction have undergone an extension.

The following are the plots of the displacement vector for the hemisphere. Both beam and truss elements were chosen for comparison. The deformation is symmetric in all the quadrants and hence only one of them is shown. The scale shows the displacement magnitudes.

(a) Beam elements: max. displ. 3.08 mm. (b) Truss elements: max. displ. 3.17 mm.

Fig. 11 Displacement magnitude plot for hemisphere

As expected and seen above, the truss elements undergo slightly larger deformations than the beam elements. Careful constraining of the unconnected elements was needed near the base of the hemisphere. Some anomalous displacement due to uneven deformation in the truss structure can still be observed in Fig. 11(b). The difference between the two structures is found to be low. The beam model provides a smoother output but takes longer time to compute.

Effect of different fabric stiffness in the two directions

Interesting results were observed when this particular case was tried. The stiffness of the weft threads was doubled and the analysis was re-performed. It was observed that the weft thread strain is also reduced to approximately half the value. Since the model takes into account the fabric stiffness and the membrane forces, a more accurate drape output can be expected.

Structural analysis of cured composites

A very useful outcome of the above analysis is that the same FE mesh was applicable, for analysing the static response of the cured composite under external forces. The same beam/truss elements are used for modelling the exact fibre orientations, but the properties of cured composites are used. The loading and boundary conditions reflect the application of the component. It is aimed to carry out deflection tests on the cured helmet specimens in future to evaluate the accuracy of this model.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented several aspects of the draping of composites, leading to the development of a prototype model for improving the draping accuracy. The basis of this work originated from the analysis of draped pattern over a helmet shape, and a comparison of the drape measurements against a kinematic model output. It was observed that the kinematic model is unable to predict accurately the shear deformation in areas of high curvature, and excludes the

fabric properties and the details of tow deformations. These secondary deformations of the tow depend not only on the on the severity of curvature but also the local membrane forces developed. Asymmetric shear tests confirmed this observation. A simple laminate theory based model is presented to predict the pre- and post-locking fabric stiffness in terms of the fibre directions. The inclusion of fabric stiffness and membrane forces into the base kinematic model leads us closer to the next generation drape model.

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REFERENCES

1. Potter, K D. "The Influence of Accurate Stretch Data for Reinforcements on the Production of Complex Structural Mouldings Part I: Deformation of Aligned Sheets and Fabrics", *Composites*, July, 1979.
2. Bergsma, O K, and Huisman, J. "Deep Drawing of Fabric Reinforced Thermoplastics", *CadComp conference*, Southampton, 1988.
3. Van West, B P, Pipes R B, and Keefe, M. "A Simulation of the Draping of Bidirectional Fabrics Over Arbitrary Surfaces", *J. Text. Inst.*, 1990, Vol. 81, No. 4, pp. 448-460.
4. A. C. Long, and C. D. Rudd, "A simulation of reinforcement deformation during the production of preforms for liquid moulding processes", *J. Engineering Manufacture, Proceedings of The Institution of Mechanical Engineers (Part B)*, 1994, Vol. 208, pp269-278.
5. "Laminate Modeler", MSC.Software Limited, UK.
6. "PAM/FORM", ESI International, France.
7. de Luca, P, Lefebure, P, and Pickett, A K. "Numerical and experimental investigations of some press forming parameters of two fibre reinforced thermoplastics: APC2-AS4 and PEI-CETEX", *Fourth Int. Conf. on Flow Processes in Composite Materials FPCM-96*, Aberystwyth, UK, 7-9 Sept, 1996.
8. Cartwright, B K, de Luca, P, Wang, J, Stellbrink, K, and Paton, R. "Some proposed experimental tests for use in finite element simulation of composite forming", *Proceedings of ICCM-12*, Paris, France, 1999.
9. Gibson, R F. "Principles of composite materials mechanics", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1994.
10. Lebrun, G, and Denault, J. "Influence of the temperature and loading rate on the intraply shear properties of a polypropylene fabric", *Proceedings of the American Society for Composites*, Technomic Publishing Co. Inc., pp 659-667, September 2000.